

Four promising medium-duration upland rice breeding lines for the République Démocratique du Congo

B. Mateso, K. Kasongo, and B. Lienge, Centre de recherches de Yangambi, Institut national pour l'étude et la recherche agronomiques (INERA), B.P. 2015, Kisangani, République Démocratique du Congo (RDC)

Several upland rice varieties have been cultivated under upland (dryland) conditions, the main rice ecosystem for RDC. Ry1 (IRAT2) is a 140-cm-high, medium-duration (120 d), blast-resistant, and lodging-tolerant variety. It was selected especially for grain yield (averaging 3.2 t ha⁻¹) and for yield stability across locations where tested. It was released in 1982 to replace R66, an old cultivar yielding 2.5 t ha⁻¹. But because RY1 rice is sticky when cooked, the cooking process is more difficult for consumers, who prefer cooked rice that is harder, flakier (not sticky), whiter, and denser in appearance and that remains soft even when stored overnight. This behavior of RY1 rice after cooking could be attributed to its low amylose content (15.6%), which has resulted in poor acceptance of RY1 by farmers.

Most of the research carried out in our breeding program involved the creation of medium-height (100-140 cm), lodging-tolerant, medium-duration (120-140 d), blast-resistant, high-yielding (more than 3 t ha⁻¹) varieties with good grain characteristics (length more than 9 mm; length to width ratio at least 3; width to thickness ratio about 1; 1,000-grain weight more than 30 g; endosperm translucency at least 60%) and good cooking quality (harder and flakier cooked rice grains).

Seven pure breeding lines (Table 1) selected from two crosses—RY1/OS6 (PR42) and OS6 × RY7/OS6 (PR55)—were compared with RY1, used as a check, during two wet crop seasons (1995 and 1996) at the Yangambi research station. At Yangambi, the soil is sandy with 20-30% clay, lighter at the

Table 1. Yields of seven selected breeding lines at Yangambi, 1995-96.

Number	Breeding line/variety Name	Mean yield (t ha ⁻¹) ^a		
		1995 crop season	1996 crop season	Av
1	PR42-44-7-8-1	2.5 abc	2.6 bcd	2.6 bc
2	PR42-44-7-8-2-1	2.4 bcd	2.4 cd	2.4 cd
3	PR42-44-7-56-1	2.3 cd	2.8 abc	2.6 bc
4	PR42-44-7-56-2	2.6 abc	3.4 a	3.0 ab
5	PR42-44-8-44-1	2.3 cd	3.3 abc	2.7 abc
6	PR55-3-1-18-3	1.9 d	2.1 d	2.0 d
7	PR55-5-2-17-16	2.9 ab	3.2 ab	3.0 a
8	RY1 (IRAT2, check)	3.0 a	3.0 abc	3.0 ab
Av		2.5	2.8	2.7
CV (%)		13.7	13.6	10.4

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letters do not differ significantly from each other at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Plant characteristics of seven selected breeding lines at Yangambi, RDC (av of 2-yr observations).

Characteristic	Breeding lines/varieties number							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Duration (d)	120	119	119	125	120	120	120	125
Plant height (cm)	121	118	123	126	126	118	120	116
Lodging (score) ^a	1	1	3	3	3	1	1	1
Grain length (mm)	9.55	9.88	9.74	9.40	9.95	9.70	9.56	10.01
Grain width (mm)	3.32	3.47	3.69	3.69	3.64	3.60	3.66	3.59
Grain thickness (mm)	2.47	2.46	2.44	2.48	2.47	2.53	2.52	2.51
L/W	2.88	2.85	2.64	2.55	2.73	2.69	2.61	2.79
1,000-grain weight (g)	38.4	39.0	44.0	40.0	36.5	40.5	42.3	37.5
Translucency (%)	60.5	49.7	38.7	63.3	60.0	53.4	65.0	58.6
Disease reactions ^a								
Brown spot	MR	MR	MS	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR
Leaf blast	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR
Leaf scald	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible.

surface than deeper. Annual rainfall and monthly temperature average 1,885 mm and 24 °C, respectively. The 2-yr experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Plots were 3 m × 6 m, in which 4-5 grains hill⁻¹ were sown at 30 × 20-cm spacing. No fertilization was used.

On average, life cycle, lodging tolerance, plant height, reaction to brown leaf spot, leaf blast, and leaf scald were similar for the breeding lines and the check RY2 (Table 2). Grain quality characteristics of the breeding lines, except for endosperm translucency, were good and also comparable with those of RY1. But yield potential

and endosperm translucency varied among the materials tested. Four breeding lines (PR42-44-7-8-1, PR42-44-7-56-2, PR42-44-8-44-1, and PR55-5-2-17-16) had yield potential comparable with that of RY1 (Table 1) and endosperm translucency above or equal to the minimum required for market acceptability. These lines were selected for testing in different INERA sub-stations located in rice-growing zones of the country.

The materials selected could eventually be recommended either for cultivation to replace RY1 or for use in breeding programs which aim to develop cultivars with high and stable yield potential and good cooking quality. ■